

Perfluoroalkyl acids interact with major human blood protein fibrinogen: Experimental and computation study

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ABSTRACT

PFAS (*per*- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances) are synthetic compounds prized for their stability across various industries, but they pose an increasing threat to the environment and human health. Following the regulation of long-chain PFAS, short-chain and ultra-short-chain molecules have been introduced as substitutes, yet their bioaccumulation potential remains poorly understood. In this study, we combined experimental (intrinsic fluorescence, microscale thermophoresis, clotting assays) and computational approaches to investigate how trifluoroacetic acid, perfluorobutanoic acid, and perfluorooctanoic acid bind to fibrinogen, a key human blood protein. All tested perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs) exhibited moderate binding affinity (K_d in the 10^{-4} – 10^{-5} M range), yet circular dichroism and fibrin clot formation assays revealed no functional impairment of fibrinogen. Molecular docking indicated distinct, chain-length-specific binding sites, suggesting multiple routes for PFAAs to interact with fibrinogen without disrupting its primary biological role. These findings challenge the assumption that short-chain PFAS are less bioaccumulative and underscore the need for further research into their long-term health impacts, particularly given their widespread presence in the environment and potential accumulation in human blood.

1. Introduction

PFAS (*per*- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances) are aliphatic organic compounds characterized by the general chemical structure $-C_nF_{2n+1}$, where n is at least 1 [1]. PFAS comprise a structurally diverse class of over 4700 synthetic molecules widely used in consumer and industrial products for their ability to impart stain, oil, and flame resistance [2–4]. PFAS are critical to high-performance products such as semiconductors, polymers, and medical devices, with no known alternatives that match their durability and longevity [3–5]. A portion of PFAS is released into the environment during production and throughout the life cycle of manufactured goods, leading to contamination of food and water [6]. However, the same extraordinary stability and durability that make PFAS valuable in industrial manufacturing now pose a significant threat to the environment and human health

[2,7]. The high energy of C–F bonds renders PFAS resistant to degradation by both biotic and abiotic processes, leading to their gradual accumulation in humans over time [8,9], leading to chronic health effects such as cancer [10–12], abnormal immune system function [13,14], hormonal disruption [15–17], kidney [18–20] and liver diseases [21–24], adverse reproductive and developmental outcomes [25–27].

Perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs) are a major class of non-polymeric PFAS, consisting of a perfluorinated hydrophobic tail and a hydrophilic head group, such as carboxylate, phosphate, or sulfonate. The perfluorinated tails vary in length, allowing PFAAs to be categorized based on chain length: ultrashort-chain molecules (2–3 fully fluorinated carbon atoms), such as trifluoroacetic acid (TFA); short-chain molecules (4–7 fully fluorinated carbon atoms), such as perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA); and long-chain molecules (eight or more fully fluorinated

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carbon atoms), such as perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) [28,29]. Most known human health issues related to PFAS exposure have been linked to PFOA. Concerns about their impact on human health first arose when high levels of PFAAs were detected in human blood [30,31] and biota [8] correlating with various health problems. Since then, many long-chain PFAS, including PFOA, have been classified as substances of very high concern under the European Chemicals Regulation (REACH) [28]. These substances are now classified as “legacy PFAS” [32] and remain highly abundant in the environment [4]. With the regulation of long-chain PFAAs and voluntary phase-outs, non-regulated molecules—primarily short-chain PFAAs, known as “emerging PFAS” [32] have been introduced as replacements [28,33]. Short-chain PFAS are generally assumed to have a lower bioaccumulation potential [1]. However, these molecules are just as persistent as long-chain PFAAs and exhibit high mobility due to their strong water solubility, increasing their potential for long-range transport [28,33,34]. Moreover, short-chain PFAAs accumulate in the edible parts of plants [28,35,36]. Long-chain PFAAs can degrade in the environment into shorter-chain PFAAs, that are the final degradation products [37,38]. Recent studies indicate that ultra-short-chain PFAAs, such as trifluoroacetic acid and perfluoropropionic acid, are the predominant PFAS found in drinking water, households, and human blood [37–39]. These values vary depending on experimental conditions, geographical location, sample types, and other influencing factors [40].

Given the high concentrations of these molecules detected in human blood, it is crucial to study and understand their effects on biological processes, as well as their transport and accumulation pathways. Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) has been shown to accumulate in platelet membranes, altering membrane fluidity and increasing cytosolic calcium levels, ultimately leading to platelet aggregation [41]. Additionally, multiple binding pockets for perfluorinated molecules have been identified in human serum albumin, the primary blood transport protein [42]; however, the binding and effects of perfluorinated molecules on other major human blood proteins remain unexplored.

Human fibrinogen, produced by liver hepatocytes, is a crucial glycoprotein involved in processes such as angiogenesis, inflammation, and blood coagulation. Biochemical analysis has revealed that fibrinogen is composed of α , β , and γ chains, linked by 29 disulfide bonds, with a relative molecular mass of approximately 340 kDa [43,44]. The 45 nm long, rod-shaped fibrinogen molecule is organized into a central E region and two distal D regions, forming a linear D-E-D domain arrangement. The E region contains fibrinopeptides FpA and FpB, which are cleaved by thrombin during blood clotting. These fibrinopeptides facilitate protofibril lateral assembly by binding to complementary sites in the D domain and the γ -nodule of another fibrin molecule [45,46]. Fibrinogen, an acute-phase protein, has a biological half-life of 3 to 5 days and is typically present in healthy individuals at concentrations of 2–5 mg/mL, potentially exceeding 7 mg/mL during inflammation [47]. During coagulation, soluble fibrinogen is converted into insoluble fibrin through thrombin-mediated cleavage and the removal of fibrinopeptides, as previously described [48]. This process facilitates the half-staggered assembly of fibrin monomers into protofibrils, forming a fibrin mesh that stabilizes blood clots [47]. The blood clotting cascade produces a network in the form of a highly extensible and insoluble hydrogel. As a major plasma protein, fibrinogen binds various small molecules in circulation, including dihydro- α -lipoic acid and vitamin C [49,50].

“Emerging” PFAS molecules are generally considered less bioaccumulative than long-chain PFAS; however, limited studies support this assumption, and their effects on human health remain largely unknown. In this study, we employ both experimental techniques and molecular docking analysis to determine whether perfluorinated molecules spanning ultra-short, short, and long-chain classes can bioaccumulate through binding to fibrinogen and whether this interaction affects the protein's function. While we do not observe a significant impact of PFAAs binding on blood clot formation, our findings reveal

that perfluorinated molecules from each class bind to distinct sites on fibrinogen, suggesting a previously unrecognized pathway for their transport and accumulation in human blood. These results underscore the need for further research into the potential long-term health effects of PFAAs accumulation in the bloodstream.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Fibrinogen was purified (Section 2.2) from a pooled sample of human plasma obtained from volunteers. PFAAs (TFA, PFBA, and PFOA) were purchased from Sigma (Germany), along with calcium chloride, $10 \times$ Dulbecco's Phosphate-Buffered Saline (dPBS), and fluorogenic thrombin substrate III. Human thrombin was obtained from Human (Germany). A 2 mM stock solution of PFAAs was prepared by dissolving them in $1 \times$ dPBS (157 mM Na^+ , 140 mM Cl^- , 4.45 mM K^+ , 10.1 mM HPO_4^{2-} , 1.76 mM H_2PO_4^-) or 50 mM Tris buffer (pH 7.4). Tris buffer was used in experiments requiring calcium chloride, while commercial dPBS buffer was used for all other experiments. All chemicals were of analytical grade. The study was approved by the local ethics committee at the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Chemistry (decision number: 4–6/24).

2.2. Isolation of fibrinogen from human blood

Venous blood was obtained from the pooled plasma of eight apparently healthy volunteers (four men and four women) aged 30–50 years. Fibrinogen was prepared using the double ammonium sulfate precipitation method [51]. Blood was collected and centrifuged for five minutes at 3000 rpm at room temperature. A saturated ammonium sulfate solution was then added to the supernatant to reach a final concentration of 20 %, and the plasma was incubated at 4 °C for one hour. The plasma was subsequently centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 min at 10 °C. The resulting supernatant was dissolved in a minimal volume of $1 \times$ dPBS (pH 7.4), followed by the addition of saturated ammonium sulfate solution to achieve the same final concentration. The mixture was incubated at 4 °C for 30 min and then centrifuged again at 8000 rpm for 10 min at 10 °C. The precipitate was dissolved in a minimal volume of $1 \times$ dPBS (pH 7.4). Protein concentration was determined at 280 nm using an extinction coefficient ($\epsilon^{1\%} = 15.1$ for fibrinogen). Purity of the product was confirmed by reducing SDS-PAGE.

2.3. Determination of binding constant of PFAAs to fibrinogen

2.3.1. Intrinsic protein fluorescence quenching method

The association constant (K_a) of PFAAs binding to fibrinogen was determined using the standard fluorescence quenching titration method. Fluorescence spectra were recorded for fibrinogen alone (40 nM) and in the presence of increasing ligand concentrations (3.33, 6.66, 9.99, 13.32, 16.65, 19.98, 23.31, and 26.64 μM) using a FluoroMax®-4 spectrofluorometer (HORIBA Scientific, Japan) at 37 °C, with all measurements performed in triplicate. An appropriate blank was used to correct for background fluorescence. The excitation wavelength was set to 280 nm to excite tryptophan (Trp) and tyrosine (Tyr) residues, and emission spectra were recorded from 290 to 500 nm with two accumulations, using a slit width of 5 nm. The binding constant, K_a , for the PFAA/fibrinogen complex was calculated using the following Eq. (1), where F_0 and F are the emission signals of the fibrinogen in the absence and presence of PFAAs, while C represents the molar concentration of the ligand (PFAAs) (1):

$$\log \frac{F_0 - F}{F} = n \times \log C + n \times \log K_a \quad (1)$$

Eq. 1 was derived from published Eq. 20 from [52], by omitting protein

concentration term, since protein concentration is significantly lower than ligand concentration.

2.3.2. Microscale thermophoresis (MST) method

The association constant of PFAAs binding to fibrinogen was also determined using the microscale thermophoresis (MST) method. A serial dilution of PFAAs was prepared in $1 \times$ dPBS buffer (pH 7.4). Each PFAA dilution was mixed with an equal volume of labeled fibrinogen, resulting in a final fibrinogen concentration of 20 nM. The final PFAAs concentration ranged from 0.74 μ M to 0.97 mM for PFBA and from 0.24 μ M to 0.50 mM for TFA and PFOA. Fibrinogen was labeled using the RED-NHS 2nd Generation Protein Labeling Kit (NanoTemper Technologies GmbH, Munich, Germany). According to the manufacturer's instructions, 10 μ L of protein was mixed with 90 μ L of supplied labeling buffer (130 mM NaHCO₃, 50 mM NaCl, pH 8.2–8.3) at room temperature, maintaining a molar dye-to-fibrinogen ratio of 3:1. The supplied dye removal column was equilibrated with 10 mM PBS (pH 7.4) to eliminate unreacted dye. Fibrinogen molar concentration (C_{fbrn}) and the degree of labeling (DOL) were calculated using Eqs. (2) and (3) in accordance with user manual for Protein Labeling Kit RED-NHS 2nd Generation (NanoTemper):

$$C_{\text{fbrn}}(M) = \frac{A_{280} - (A_{650} \times 0.04)}{\varepsilon_{280} \times d} \quad (2)$$

$$DOL = \frac{A_{650}}{195 \times 10^3 M^{-1} cm^{-1} \times C_{\text{fbrn}}(M)} \quad (3)$$

Where ε_{280} is the molar extinction coefficient of fibrinogen at 280 nm, d is the path length of a spectrophotometer in cm, and 0.04 is a correction factor at 280 nm. The samples were loaded into the Monolith™ NT. Automated capillary Chips (NanoTemper Technologies GmbH, Munich, Germany) and incubated for 15 min. Capillaries were then placed in the Monolith NT. Automated instrument (NanoTemper Technologies GmbH, Munich, Germany). MST power was set to 40 %, and the excitation type was Nano Red. The results were analyzed with MO. Affinity Analysis v2.3 software (NanoTemper Technologies GmbH, Munich, Germany) using the signal from MST over a 2.5-s time period. This enabled the estimation of the dissociation constant (K_d) using the law of mass action. The K_d was determined using the following Eq. (4) in accordance with manufacturer's instructions for fitting function for K_d from the law of mass action (NanoTemper):

$$f(C) = \text{unbound} + (\text{bound} - \text{unbound}) \times \frac{C + C_{\text{target}} + K_d - \sqrt{(C + C_{\text{target}} + K_d)^2 - 4 \times C \times C_{\text{target}}}}{2 \times C_{\text{target}}} \quad (4)$$

The function $f(C)$ represents the fraction bound at the given ligand (PFAAs) concentration C . “Unbound” refers to the normalized signal (F_{norm}) of the target (protein) alone. “Bound” refers to the normalized signal (F_{norm}) of the target-ligand complex. K_d is the equilibrium dissociation constant, and C_{target} denotes the final concentration of the target in the assay.

2.4. CD spectrometric measurements

Circular dichroism (CD) spectrometric analysis of the interaction between fibrinogen and ligands (TFA, PFBA, and PFOA) was conducted using a Jasco J-815 spectropolarimeter (Jasco, Tokyo, Japan) at 37 °C. The scan speed was set to 50 nm/min. Fibrinogen and ligands were dissolved in $1 \times$ dPBS (pH 7.4), with ligand stock concentrations of 2

mM. For near-UV measurements (260–320 nm) using a 1 cm path length cell, fibrinogen was used at a concentration of 0.5 mg/mL, while PFAAs were tested at 50 μ M and 100 μ M. Far-UV measurements (190–260 nm) were performed under the same conditions but using a 0.01 cm path length cell.

The content of secondary structures was further estimated using the CONTIN algorithm available within the CDPro software package. SP29 database was used. For this analysis, far CD spectra were first converted to mean residue ellipticity (MRE) using the following Eq. (5):

$$[MRE] = \frac{\theta \times Mm}{10 \times l \times C \times r} \quad (5)$$

Where MRE has the units of mdeg \times cm² / dmol, θ is ellipticity in units of mdeg, Mm is molar mass of fibrinogen (340,000 g/mol), l is the optical path length (0.01 cm), C is concentration of fibrinogen (0.5 mg/mL) and r is the number of amino acid residues in fibrinogen (2970 amino acids) [53].

2.5. Spectrophotometric analysis of fibrin clot formation

Analysis of influence of PFAAs on fibrin clot formation was performed using Cary 3500 Multicell UV–Vis Spectrophotometer at 280 nm and 350 nm at 37 °C. Kinetic measurements were recorded for a mixture containing PFAAs (TFA, PFBA, or PFOA) at final concentrations of 50 μ M, 100 μ M, and 200 μ M in 50 mM Tris buffer (pH 7.4) with 0.7 mg/mL fibrinogen. Clotting was initiated by adding either 0.025 IU/mL or 1 IU/mL thrombin along with 2.5 mM calcium chloride solution. A control sample, containing fibrinogen, thrombin, and calcium chloride in the same concentrations but without PFAAs, was used for comparison. Absorbance was recorded every 90 s for 30 min. Before fibrin initiation, the PFAAs-fibrinogen mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 10 min.

To accurately assess fibrin formation, measuring only absorbance changes due to protein aggregate formation is insufficient, as aggregates can obstruct light passage. Therefore, it is essential to introduce a parameter that accounts for light scattering, such as the aggregation index (AI) [54,55]. The AI parameter is defined according to the following Eq. (6):

$$AI = \frac{A_{350}}{A_{280} - A_{350}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where A_{280} and A_{350} are the measured absorbance at 280 and 350 nm, respectively. All AI (aggregation index) data is represented with standard deviation (\pm SD) in multiplicate.

2.6. The impact of PFAAs on thrombin activity - fluorometric assay

We investigated the changes in thrombin activity in the presence and absence of TFA, PFBA, and PFOA. Thrombin substrate III fluorogenic (Sigma-Aldrich, Sent Louis, Missouri, USA) was dissolved in a $1 \times$ dPBS. The assay was performed with the thrombin concentration of 0.025 IU/mL. Activity of thrombin was followed in time using 360 nm excitation and 440 nm emission.

2.7. Computational study of interactions between PFAAs and fibrinogen

Docking study of the PFAAs binding to fibrinogen E region was performed on 3D crystal structure of fibrinogen (PDB ID: 3GHG) [56]. However, 3GHG covers only 66 % of fibrinogen structure counted by amino acids present in the full protein sequence; therefore, the analysis of other regions was performed using augmented structure (78 % of the total sequence) proposed by Klykov et al., using cross-linking mass spectrometry (XL-MS) method on fibrin [57]. The protonation state of each titratable amino acid was determined using the H++ 3.0 program [58]. Geometries of trifluoroacetic acid, perfluorobutanoic acid, and perfluorooctanoic acid were optimized using B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) method in Gaussian09 program [59]. AutoDockTools (version 1.5.7.) [60] was used to prepare protein and ligands structures for docking and to add appropriate partial atomic charges. Due to large size of fibrinogen the molecular docking was conducted in large number of smaller grid boxes ($24 \times 24 \times 24 \text{ \AA}$) that were shifted by 8 \AA in one direction in each docking run. A total of 3840 grid boxes were necessary to cover full fibrinogen structure. During docking runs, protein residues were kept rigid and rotational freedom of ligands' single bonds was retained. The AutoDockVina program [61] was utilized for the purpose of conducting docking simulations and estimating binding energies (kcal/mol). Discovery Studio (2024) and PyMOL2 were employed for the purpose of visualizing the results.

2.8. Statistical analysis of data

Fibrinogen intrinsic fluorescence measurements and the spectrofluorimetric assay assessing the influence of PFAAs binding on thrombin activity were performed in triplicate. The spectrophotometric assay evaluating the effect of PFAAs binding on fibrin clot formation was conducted in quadruplicate. All experimental data are presented as mean values with standard deviation. Data processing was carried out using OriginPro software (OriginLab Corporation, USA), and statistical

analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by a Post Hoc Tukey test, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Binding of PFAAs to fibrinogen - intrinsic protein fluorescence quenching measurements

To determine whether perfluorinated molecules of varying chain lengths (Fig. S1) can accumulate in the human body by binding to a major blood protein, fibrinogen, intrinsic fibrinogen fluorescence measurements were first conducted in the presence of trifluoroacetic acid (TFA), perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA), and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) at increasing concentrations.

All proteins containing aromatic amino acids, such as tryptophan and tyrosine, exhibit intrinsic fluorescence. This property is widely used to study protein-ligand interactions, as the fluorescence of aromatic amino acids is sensitive to changes in their microenvironment induced by small molecule binding. In the presence of all tested ligands, a decrease in fibrinogen's intrinsic fluorescence is observed, which correlates with increasing ligand concentrations, as shown in Fig. 1, panels A–C.

Ligand concentrations were selected based on previous studies employing the same methodology, and affinity binding constants were calculated using Eq. 1 (see Methods section) [62–65]. The logarithmic value of the change in emitted intrinsic fluorescence of fibrinogen at each ligand concentration, normalized to the fluorescence of the protein in the absence of ligand, was plotted against the logarithmic value of ligand concentration. This approach established a linear relationship between fluorescence change and ligand concentration, allowing for the calculation of binding affinity constants, as shown in Fig. 1, panels D–F. The ligand dissociation constant was defined as the reciprocal of K_a (Table 1). The results indicate that fibrinogen binds to TFA with the highest affinity, with a K_d of $8.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, followed by PFBA and PFOA,

Fig. 1. Representative emission spectra of fibrinogen titrated with increasing concentrations of: (A) TFA; (B) PFBA and (C) PFOA. The plot generated from Eq. 1 for determination of the affinity constant between fibrinogen and (D) TFA; (E) PFBA and (F) PFOA.

Table 1

Dissociation constants for PFAAs binding to fibrinogen, determined by fluorometric measurements and microscale thermophoresis (MST), along with binding energies estimated by molecular docking.

TFA	PFBA	PFOA
Ligand dissociation constants (K_d /M) obtained with intrinsic fluorescence measurements		
$8.9 \times 10^{-5} \pm 1.4 \times 10^{-5}$	$1.6 \times 10^{-4} \pm 0.5 \times 10^{-4}$	$2.1 \times 10^{-4} \pm 0.4 \times 10^{-4}$
Ligand dissociation constants (K_d /M) obtained with MST		
$1.21 \times 10^{-5} \pm 0.24 \times 10^{-5}$	$2.51 \times 10^{-5} \pm 0.58 \times 10^{-5}$	$1.07 \times 10^{-5} \pm 0.28 \times 10^{-5}$
Binding energies for E region estimated by molecular docking (kcal/mol)		
-4.3	-6.5	-8.9
-4.1	-5.8	-6.9
-4.0		-6.8
Binding energies for modeled protein estimated by molecular docking (kcal/mol)		
-4.7	-6.1	-8.6
-4.4	-5.6	-8.5
-4.4	-5.6	-7.8

with K_d values of 1.6×10^{-4} M and 2.1×10^{-4} M, respectively. These findings suggest that all three tested ligands bind to fibrinogen with moderate affinity [66], and that shorter-chain molecules exhibit slightly higher binding affinity. Moreover, one way ANOVA test has shown that only K_d calculated for PFOA and TFA are statistically significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.2. Binding of PFAAs to fibrinogen - microscale thermophoresis measurements

Although intrinsic fluorescence quenching is a widely used and accepted method for characterizing protein-ligand interactions, it has a limitation: fluorescence changes are highly dependent on the proximity of the ligand to one or more aromatic amino acids. In large proteins, if a ligand binds far from the region containing these residues, the resulting microenvironmental changes may be minimal, potentially leading to inaccuracies.

To confirm the binding of perfluorinated acids to fibrinogen, a more precise technique, Microscale Thermophoresis (MST), was employed. This method measures the movement of a fluorescently labeled protein within a glass capillary tube under infrared laser-induced microscopic temperature gradients in the presence of increasing ligand concentrations. The protein's ability to migrate through a temperature gradient is

influenced by its binding interactions with different molecules. Consequently, ligand binding alters the thermophoretic behavior of the protein, which is then quantified to assess the strength and specificity of the interactions.

MST measurements were performed for all three PFAAs, and the ligand dissociation constant (K_d) was calculated using the law of mass action (Fig. 2, Table 1). The K_d values for TFA, PFBA, and PFOA were determined to be 1.21×10^{-5} M, 2.51×10^{-5} M, and 1.07×10^{-5} M, respectively. These values indicate a stronger binding affinity for all tested ligands compared to intrinsic fluorescence measurements; however, the binding affinities remain within the moderate range for each ligand. Additionally, one way ANOVA test has shown that only K_d calculated for PFOA and TFA are statistically significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Although the differences between the K_d values among the PFAAs are small, these results suggest that perfluorinated molecules of varying chain lengths bind to distinct regions of fibrinogen. The binding site for TFA may be located closer to aromatic amino acids compared to the regions where PFBA or PFOA bind.

3.3. The binding effect of PFAAs on fibrinogen structure

Since both intrinsic fluorescence measurements and MST confirmed the binding of PFAAs to fibrinogen, CD spectra were recorded in the presence of all three ligands to assess whether ligand binding influences fibrinogen's structure. No significant changes are observed in the intensity or shape of either the near-UV or far-UV CD spectra of fibrinogen in the presence of PFAAs (Fig. 3A and B). Furthermore, no shifts in the wavelengths of characteristic minima or maxima are detected, and the percentage of α -helices, which are the predominant secondary structural motifs in fibrinogen, as well as β -sheets, remained unchanged across different PFAAs concentrations. Given that fibrinogen is a large fibrillar protein, these results were expected.

To further assess the impact of PFAAs binding on fibrinogen's secondary structure, CD Pro analysis was performed. The results confirmed that fibrinogen's secondary structure remained unchanged in the presence of PFAAs at both 50 and 100 μ M concentrations (Fig. S2). Regarding fibrinogen's tertiary structure, three regions from the near-UV CD spectra are of particular interest: the tryptophan (Trp) region (290–305 nm), the tyrosine (Tyr) region (275–282 nm), and the phenylalanine (Phe) region (255–270 nm) [67]. The results indicate that changes in these regions are minimal; however, the most pronounced alterations occur in the Tyr and Phe regions. These findings suggest a tendency for loosening, as evidenced by the reduction in ellipticity, of the tertiary structure around Tyr and Phe residues, particularly in the presence of PFBA.

Fig. 2. Results of the MST experiment, obtained from the fibrinogen titration with increasing concentrations of: (A) TFA; (B) PFBA and (C) PFOA ligands. The error bars represent the standard deviation for each data point, calculated from two independent measurements.

Fig. 3. The analysis of the secondary and tertiary structure of fibrinogen in presence of two different concentrations of PFAAs. (A) The overlaid CD spectrum in the far UV region of fibrinogen in presence of PFAAs. (B) The overlaid CD spectrum in the near UV region of fibrinogen in presence of PFAAs.

3.4. The binding effect of PFAAs on fibrinogen capability to form fibrin

The blood clotting process involves thrombin-mediated proteolytic cleavage of fibrinogen molecules, followed by their rearrangement and polymerization into fibrin fibers, ultimately leading to blood clot formation. To assess whether PFAAs binding influences fibrin fiber formation and interferes with the clotting process, it was first necessary to confirm that PFAAs do not affect thrombin activity. Thrombin was preincubated with increasing concentrations of PFAAs before the addition of a fluorogenic substrate, and fluorescence changes were monitored over time. No effect of PFAAs within the tested concentration range on thrombin activity is observed (Fig. S3). Consequently, the influence of PFAAs on fibrin fiber formation is further investigated.

This was assessed by measuring the clot aggregation index (AI) for fibrinogen-thrombin and fibrinogen-PFAAs-thrombin mixtures over time. The aggregation index is a key parameter used to evaluate protein stability and its propensity to form aggregates [54,55]. Following the initiation of the clotting reaction, absorbance was monitored at 350 nm and 280 nm to account for light scattering effects. The aggregation index (AI) was calculated after 30 min as the ratio of A_{350} to the difference in

absorbance at 280 and 350 nm, as shown in Fig. 4. The results indicate that fibrillary networks formed at the same rate, regardless of PFAA concentration in solution. Therefore, it can be concluded that the binding of PFAAs to fibrinogen does not significantly impact its function or its ability to facilitate blood clot formation.

3.5. Molecular docking of fibrinogen/PFAA complex

To gain deeper insight into the binding of PFAAs to fibrinogen, a comprehensive molecular docking study was conducted. AutoDock Vina was used to systematically search the entire protein for potential PFAA binding sites. To achieve thorough coverage, the protein was divided into more than three thousand partially overlapping grid boxes. This approach, which utilizes a large number of small grid boxes, has proven highly effective in previous studies involving large proteins [68]. Molecular docking was initially performed on the human fibrinogen crystal structure available in the Protein Data Bank (PDB ID: 3GHG). Several high-affinity binding sites for PFAAs are identified, predominantly located in the E region of fibrinogen, as shown in Fig. 5A. The highest binding energies in this region were estimated to be -8.9 kcal/mol for

Fig. 4. Influence of bound PFAAs on functionality of fibrinogen. (A) The increase in fibrinogen aggregation index over time in presence of TFA, PFBA and PFOA. (B) The change in aggregation index during the formation of fibrinogen fibril in the presence of different concentrations of PFAAs.

Fig. 5. (A) The highest energy binding sites for TFA (cyan carbon atoms); PFBA (magenta carbon atoms) and PFOA (yellow carbon atoms) in E region of fibrinogen. (B) 2-D interaction diagrams for TFA, PFBA and PFOA with amino acids from fibrinogen E region.

PFOA, -6.5 kcal/mol for PFBA, and -4.3 kcal/mol for TFA (Table 1).

All three ligands were found to bind to the E region in a similar manner. Hydrogen bonds were formed between the oxygen of the carboxyl head and Thr22 of the γ chain, while fluorine interactions were

observed with Pro20 of the γ chain, as well as Pro77, Thr78, and Gly79 of the β chain, as illustrated in the 2D diagrams in Fig. 5B. Estimated binding energies were lower for smaller molecules, as they established fewer interactions. Due to their longer fluorinated tails, PFBA and PFOA

Fig. 6. (A) The highest energy binding sites for TFA, PFBA, and PFOA outside of E region of fibrinogen. (B) 2-D interaction diagrams for TFA, PFBA and PFOA with amino acids binding sites shown in panel A.

formed more interactions with fibrinogen than TFA.

However, only approximately 66 % of the human fibrinogen structure has been resolved by X-ray crystallography (PDB ID: 3GHG) at a resolution of 2.90 Å. The unresolved regions, primarily the highly flexible α -C domain, could not be determined with high confidence. To address this limitation, the fibrinogen structure was further modeled based on one half of the symmetric protein, incorporating data from a previous study [57]. Molecular docking was then performed on the modeled fibrinogen structure, revealing multiple high-affinity binding sites for all three molecules (Table 1). Newly identified high-affinity binding sites for TFA and PFOA were located in the D region of fibrinogen, while PFBA remained bound in the E region but at a different site, as shown in Fig. 6A and Table 1.

The interaction of TFA with fibrinogen involved several amino acids with hydrophobic side chains and one positively charged residue. Docking results indicated that TFA binds to amino acids in the γ chain of the D region, with this binding site exhibiting significantly higher binding energy compared to the previously identified site in the E region. The tryptophan residue TrpC:360 formed hydrogen bonds with both the oxygen atom from the carboxyl group and a fluorine atom from the TFA molecule. Additionally, TrpC:361 established a halogen bond with fluorine from the tail, while HisC:333 formed a carbon-hydrogen bond with the same fluorine atom. Further stabilization of TFA was achieved through additional van der Waals interactions.

The ligand PFBA was found to bind to the E region of fibrinogen via nonpolar amino acids, forming halogen (fluorine) interactions with Val127 and Leu130 from the β chain. The longest-chain PFAA, PFOA, exhibited strong binding to the disordered part of the D region. A salt bridge was formed between ArgB:224 of the β chain and both the fluorine in the tail and the oxygen of the carboxyl group. Binding was further stabilized through numerous halogen interactions between fluorine and various amino acids from the β and γ chains, as illustrated in the 2D diagrams in Fig. 6B. Additional high-binding energy positions for all PFAAs are provided in Supplementary Table S1 and Fig. S4.

Moreover, intrinsic fluorescence measurements in the presence of PFAAs indicated that TFA binds to fibrinogen with the highest affinity, while MST results showed that PFOA exhibits a stronger binding affinity than TFA. These findings suggest that perfluorinated molecules of varying chain lengths bind to distinct regions of fibrinogen, with TFA preferentially binding to a region rich in tryptophan (Trp) and tyrosine (Tyr) residues.

Molecular docking further supports these observations, as the highest-energy binding site for TFA includes direct interactions with TrpC:360 and TrpC:361, while also being in close proximity to TrpC:395 (Fig. 6B and S5). Additionally, two Tyr residues were identified near the PFBA binding site, whereas no aromatic residues were found near the PFOA binding site (Fig. 6B and S5). These findings further confirm that the MST results provide the most accurate binding affinity estimates, indicating that PFOA binds to fibrinogen with slightly higher affinity than TFA.

Recent studies have demonstrated the toxic effects of various PFAS compounds, which can mimic endogenous substances. These compounds have been shown to bind to membranes and proteins, such as L-FABP, OAT, and HSA, initiating molecular events and influencing signaling processes [69]. The binding of PFAS to fibrinogen observed in this study aligns with the findings of Fedorenko et al. (2021). In the HSA–PFAS complex model, the hydrophobic tail demonstrated greater binding affinity than the hydrophilic head [70]. This suggests that the stronger binding of PFAS to HSA can be attributed to the higher hydrophobicity of these compounds. Furthermore, experimental data from Gao et al. [71] indicate that the dissociation constant (K_d) for HSA–PFAS binding ranges from 0.01 mM to 1 mM, demonstrating a moderate binding affinity of PFAS for HSA. These findings are consistent with those of a related study [72], that confirms a similar binding behavior for human hemoglobin.

Additionally, when evaluating structural changes in proteins upon

PFAS binding, the CD spectroscopic results obtained in this study were found to be consistent with those reported in the aforementioned study [72], suggesting that PFAS have a negligible impact on the secondary structure of proteins. Furthermore, PFAS were found to have no significant effect on the activity of bovine catalase, which aligns with the findings of this study, demonstrating no notable impact on the functions of fibrinogen and thrombin [73]. Due to the complexity of the blood clotting process, the binding of these harmful molecules to fibrinogen, which has a half-life of approximately four days, may still influence its conversion into fibrin by affecting interactions with other molecules involved in the formation of primary and secondary blood clots. Additionally, since PFAS have been shown to incorporate into platelet membranes, this raises the question of whether fibrinogen could facilitate the transport of PFAS molecules into direct contact with platelets during clot formation [41,69,74].

4. Conclusion

With the regulation of long-chain PFAAs, new shorter-chain molecules have emerged. For example, TFA is now the most abundant perfluorinated molecule detected in drinking water. These short- and ultra-short-chain molecules are generally considered less bioaccumulative and, therefore, less of a threat to human and animal health. However, our computational and experimental results demonstrate that both PFBA and TFA bind to the major human blood protein, fibrinogen, with an affinity comparable to that of PFOA.

Together with liver, kidneys and bones, blood is considered a primary accumulation vessel for PFAS [75,76]. Moreover, since the liver plays a key role in the metabolism of many blood proteins, a clear correlation has been established between PFAS levels in human blood and the liver [76]. Even if the binding of PFAAs does not interfere with fibrinogen's function, this protein may serve as a route for the bioaccumulation and transport of both “legacy” and “emerging” perfluorinated molecules.

These findings challenge the assumption that short-chain PFAS are less bioaccumulative and underscore the need for further research into their potential long-term health effects. Additionally, it is crucial to investigate whether other blood proteins are similarly affected by PFAS binding and whether this interaction disrupts their normal biological functions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Aleksandra Đurđević Delmaš: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Tino Šeba:** Visualization, Investigation. **Nikola Gligorijević:** Methodology, Investigation. **Marko Pavlović:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources. **Maja Gruđen:** Validation, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Milan Nikolić:** Methodology, Conceptualization. **Karla Milčić:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Miloš Milčić:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors confirm that there are no financial or personal relationships that could have influenced the findings presented in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.141425>.

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